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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the poetic morphology of the Azerbaijani language. All areas of the language play a certain role in poetry. In this sense, morphology has great potential. The article analyzes the topic of poetic morphology in detail, refers to the work of various poets, reveals linguistic facts relevant to the topic, and involves scientific and theoretical analysis. Poetic morphology, as a field that studies the poetic forms of the language, examines both the morphological structure of the language and the aesthetic and poetic functions of parts of speech in the literary language. The article confirms that poetic morphology is a field that connects the structures and forms of the language with their specific use in poetic texts. This field studies how the morphological structure of the language is changed for aesthetic-expressive purposes, changes in form, and their poetic effect. The article analyzes the theoretical foundations of poetic morphology, the role of language in the process of semantic analysis, as well as how various poetic forms and language structures are used creatively. The study reveals how language is strengthened not only for the purpose of communication, but also as an aesthetic and expressive tool through morphological means.

Keywords: language, word, style, morphology, parts of speech, poetics.

Introduction

Poetic morphology is one of the most complex and at the same time most interesting areas of literature and language. This field, in particular, studies the role of morphology in the structure, form and methods of expression of poetic language. Poetic morphology analyzes how the morphological structure of language is specialized in poetry and other literary examples and how it is used for poetic purposes. This field of science, which is specific to the language of poetry and tries to understand the interaction between meaning and form, deepens both the aesthetic potential of language and the meanings it creates. Research in this field is needed to understand the different features of poetic language and how its morphological elements are formed for poetic purposes. Each language has its own morphological characteristics, and the involvement of poetry in the study of that language in a deep and comprehensive study results in interesting facts. In this regard, the article dedicated to the poetic morphology of the Azerbaijani language shows its relevance.

Material and methods

The research used linguistic analysis, description and comparison methods. The material focused on the creative examples of poets who lived and created in Azerbaijan at different times.

Discussion

A number of different aspects, some grammatical, especially morphological features, in the Azerbaijani poetic language have poetic linguistic richness. In this sense, we observe that ordinary words are raised to an extraordinary artistic beauty and level in Nasimi's language. Nasimi is one of the poets who reveals all the subtleties of the Azerbaijani poetic language. The repeated use of black and white adjectives, interrogative pronouns in the language of his ghazals and their placement in various stylistic moments, especially their arrangement in the structure of the interrogative sentence, attracts attention as a successful stylistic fact. "*Words,*

expressions are not only linguistic units, speech facts, but also spiritual mirrors of word masters, literary figures. Ordinary mirrors have a short life span, they can be lost, broken, or show the time when a person looks at them. The word is an eternal mirror, no matter how much time passes, it has the power to reflect a person's thoughts, desires, and spiritual world. The power of the word is always valid, it is invincible at any moment. No matter how much a word is said, if it is in the right place, a person does not get tired of it, on the contrary, he enjoys it..." (Hasanova (2017), pp. 205-206).

The ellipsis of the interrogative pronoun "what" in I. Nasimi's ghazals has a fundamental impact on the artistic quality of the language. "Ellipsis, that is, the omission of a sentence member (or any grammatical device) does not mean that it does not take its place in the appropriate syntactic position..." (Jabbarov (1986), p. 93). The sign of not taking its place in the text is manifested only from a formal point of view, that is, the elliptical language fact is always alive from a logical point of view. Another word that attracts attention in the poet's language is some verbs, which are one of the lexical-grammatical facts that have lost their place for the contemporary Azerbaijani literary language, attract attention with their beauty of expression.

Each line of one of Nasimi's ghazals begins with the name of the days of the week. The work can be assessed as an example of plot-based lyrics. The event in the ghazal creates a neat stylistic pattern with the power of morphological units and is presented with beautiful rhythmic shades reminiscent of syllable weight.

In the language of the poet Gurbani, we encounter a different expression of the present tense of the verb. This different feature is not found in historical grammar. Perhaps it was put in this form for the sake of poetry, or it was once a dialect fact.

There are lexical suffixes written in a certain order in the Azerbaijani language. One of them is the suffix -kar, which changes both the form and meaning of the

word to which it is attached. This morphological feature participates in the formation of nouns and adjectives by combining words. For example: artist, self-sacrificing, etc. In Gurbani's language, we encounter the same suffixal morpheme attached to the word master:

You named yourself a master (Gurbani (2008), p. 103).

There are words in the Azerbaijani language that were brought to the poetic language from dialects. According to some opinions, the verb "sayrışmaq" was taken from dialects and brought to our language by S. Vurgun, and the verb "yuvalanmaq" was first encountered in the language of that poet. However, studies confirm that the above-mentioned lexical-grammatical units were first created in Azerbaijani written literature in the language of Molla Panah Vagif (Vagif (2004), p. 56;124). When you get acquainted with Vagif's language, you think that "the artist is the word architect of the land. Every artist lives in the palace of words. The language of poetry is the language of a people. The fate of the word is the fate of the people. They burn like candles on the word... In the heart of a true artist, the words that make up a verse have their own order, their positions are more capacious, more meaningful, more magnificent" (Jabbarov (1986), p. 95).

The verb "yanmaq" of national origin in Azerbaijani is distinguished by its functionality and activity in word creation. However, in our language, in the language of Vagif, we find this word used in the reciprocal-joint form of the verb. The expression "to burn in the fire of love" has been used so much in lyrics that it has already become a template. However, the expression of the last component of the expression with the verb "yanışmaq", that is, "to burn together", sounds like a fresh and refreshing unit in the artistic language. "...The novelty expressed by the poet - new words, expressions, metaphors are in the works he created in the genres of folk poetry. His activity is not only in the clarity of his language, but precisely in its novelty" (Hajiyev (1979), p. 53). As one of the language units that creates artistic beauty in its internal meaning, the verb "tamanashmaq" attracts attention with its appeal to the heart. This word is used among the people in the sense of "halallaşmaq".

In our language, we find various aspects of the word "var". This word mainly means ownership. For example, the word "var" in the sentence "I have a silver belt" means "to have a silver belt." In addition, there are many cases where it is used in suffixal position. For example, as in the word "ümidvar". In such cases, the morpheme "var" appears as a synonymous variant of the suffix -li⁴.

Sometimes we come across facts that are not considered grammatically correct in the literary language. Such a feature arises from colloquial speech and is not considered a defect since it is used for stylistic purposes. Or one of M.A. Sabir's works is called "An Answer to Two Answers" (Sabir (2004), p. 80), where a feature that contradicts the grammatical rules of the Azerbaijani language is manifested. Thus, in this language, nouns that come after a certain number of quantities are not used with the plural suffix, and such a fact is a fact of violation of the grammatical norm of the lit-

erary language. The use of that suffix in Sabir's language is not an individual issue. Literary language studies of the period show that this fact is of a general nature and is observed in the language of a number of poets.

In M.A. Sabir's language, compared to our modern language, there are a number of different features, one of which, although included in the active morphology of the modern Turkic language, is already archaic for the Azerbaijani language. For example:

Does the blooming of a flower make it a season of spring?! (Sabir (2004), p. 80).

"Ya" is used in Turkish as both the negative adverb "heç" and the interrogative adverb "bes", and sometimes as an exclamation. In Sabir's language, "da2" and "ha" sometimes appear as intensifiers:

What is a lip smile, tell me? (Sabir (2004), p. 195).

Although this fact was characteristic of the early 20th century, it was not standardized later. However, recently it has been frequently used in television programs, that is, it is returning to the language. One of the distinguishing features is the processing of the negation of verbs consisting of two, and sometimes three words, as in Turkic languages, and their separate writing. .

In the Azerbaijani classical poetic language, one can find cases of dropping the final consonant in the present tense suffix of the verb. In this regard, the work of Molla Juma is characteristic (Molla Juma (2006). In Molla Juma's poems, many of the national morphological units that reduce the activity of processing in modern Azerbaijani language attract attention with their active position. We see the processing of a large number of common Turkic language units in the Ashug language.

In the old Turkic languages, a morphological feature that differs from the suffixes of the Azerbaijani language was used as the ending of the first person singular in the imperative form of the verb, which is still the case in modern Turkish Turkish. However, the aforementioned suffix, which was once attached to Azerbaijani verbs, has become archaic. Research on the linguistic and stylistic features of Molla Juma shows that this suffix was still in use in the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century.

The use of suffixes in poetic language at different times is also noteworthy.

Everyone in the world has a qibla,

I have also turned my attention towards you (Vagif (2004), p. 52).

The difference here is that while in Vagif language the directional suffixes are used with nouns in the nominative case, they are attached to the possessive case. This shows that the case suffixes of nouns also have stylistic possibilities. Such examples can also be found in S. Vurgun's language. For example:

Kura coast... Qarayazi... Goy chamen...

Old oak... Burning fire, hearth...

My hair has turned gray, I have not forgotten you,
Which poet will write about you again? (Vurgun (2005), p. 283).

Although the pronoun "sizi" in the last line is also used in the same sense, in Azerbaijani it is usually used as "sizdan" in the same context.

Speaking in the language of a poetic work, violating grammatical norms does not cause any defect. Because in artistic language style is superior to grammar and the beauty of style can cover up any defect. We observe the same feature in the following poem:

The high mountains will not burn if they fall into the fire,

They will not remember the good (Poet Bahman (2017), p. 509).

In the first line of the poem, the use of the plural suffix, which is characteristic of living things, in the dependent word in agreement with the quantity seems appropriate and creates a rhyme that increases phonopoeic possibilities and overshadows the fact of going beyond the grammatical framework. Here, the poet's operation on language comes to the fore. "The poet's creativity related to language on a literary work is not a special, personal issue, but a national issue. In general, the fate of fiction depends largely on the state of the literary language. Therefore, the issue of the language of a literary work has an important social meaning" (Adilov (2020), p. 253).

The -i morpheme that forms adjectives in Azerbaijani belongs to two groups of suffixes (both lexical and grammatical). It is grammatical as both the third person and possessive case of a noun, and has the property of homonymy as a lexical suffix that forms new words from nouns. Thus, this lexical suffix is used both as a national lexical suffix that is written in four ways and is subject to the law of harmony (for example, chestnut color, navy blue dress, silver hair), and as a borrowed lexical suffix. In such cases, this suffix does not obey the law of harmony and is attached only to borrowed words (for example, scientific work, historical event, mass work, etc.). However, there are facts in Azerbaijani that, although this suffix is attached to borrowed words, it is subject to the law of harmony. This fact becomes clear when this suffix is added to the word "hava".

In the "Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language", the meaning of the word "havayı" is given as "in vain", "unjust", "waste", "meaningless", "worthless", etc. (Explanatory Dictionary of the Azerbaijani Language, Volume II (2006), p. 336). The lexical-grammatical unit formed from that word also entered the Azerbaijani language in the form of "havayı", adapting to the original meaning of the word "hava". In the historical grammar of the Azerbaijani language, the original phonetic variant of the word is "hava". For example, in the section "Mother's Advice to Leyli" of M. Fuzuli's poem "Leyli and Majnun", her mother says to Leyli:

You are a candle, do not obey the wind,

Because the wind extinguishes the candle (Fuzuli (2008), p. 56).

It is interesting that the suffix -i in the word, although both it and the word it is attached to are of Persian origin, obeys the law of harmony, and this has been evaluated as the only distinguishing feature in the Azerbaijani language. However, a similar word in Vagif's language confirms that this fact is not unique. This fact shows the importance of approaching the suffix -i from a new perspective.

The adjective "sad" in Azerbaijani is presented with a different freshness in Vagif's language. The word "düyün", which is one of the active units of the general Turkic lexicon and means wedding, celebration, is also interesting. This word, which remains in our modern language as part of the compound noun "toy-düyün", was once used in Azerbaijani. Currently, it is one of the characteristic language elements for the Turkish language.

The appeal to Badi-saba is one of the characteristic features of Azerbaijani classical poetry. In our written literary language, there is an appeal to Saba. However, in our opinion, the appeal to "badi-saba" in works written in the spirit of the people is associated with the Vagif era. Later, we also see it in the language of S.A. Nabati:

Seba, tell me, oh lovely one,

Should the nightingale come to the garden or not?

This lover of separation, the one weary with years,

Should he come to your door for medicine, or not?

(Nebati, 2004, p. 147).

In the 19th century, we encounter this fact in the language of Q. Zakir:

Badi-saba, tell me about my beloved,

The beauties have appeared for a promenade, let them come (Zakir, 2005, p. 165).

In poetry, verb phrases expressing the subject come before the predicate, drawing logical emphasis to themselves, thus enhancing the mood in the poetic language.

It is evident from the language of the poem that verbal constructions are one of the linguistic units that affect the power of expressiveness in poetry. Due to their repetition of words, verbal constructions create interesting poetic moments in the language of the poem:

I wandered through these lands,

I arranged the flowers one by one.

Looking at the roads,

I am searching for you.

(Cabbarzadə, 2005, p. 94).

In poetic language, common nouns are used with epithets, creating a different poetic atmosphere. For example, let's look at the noun "love" in N. Kasemanli's language. The poet's poetry contains rich epithets of love, various colors: shy love, blindfolded love, crying love, short-lived love, misplaced love, old love, love that is an epic in the language, dying love, secret love, hopeless love, etc. It is possible to find enough interesting and original expressions in the language of Nusret Kasemanli to increase the number of these epithets (Kasemanli (2004).

The skillful use of the vocabulary of the Azerbaijani people in Bahman Vatenoglu's work distances his language from fabrication and serves to multiply the precious pearls of a neat style. The poet's respect and reverence for the poetic language and his words are felt in all his works. The content of this respect is formed by simple, deeply meaningful words. Bahman Vatenoglu is a man of words, far from unnecessary luxury, meaningless pathos, and unnecessary epithets.

The straight cannot take the crooked's sight,

The tyrant would not like the word of right.

When times are wicked, the world does not delight,

The wicked would bear the brunt of their plight (Vatenoglu (2020), p. 332).

In this example, there is a noteworthy fact from the linguistic point of view. In the context of the poem, the word “yaman” is one of the national lexical-grammatical units. In dictionaries, this word is correctly included in the adjective zone in terms of its general grammatical meaning. However, language and speech materials confirm the homonymy of the word “yaman” and show its use as both an adjective and an adverb. Examples taken from Bahman Vatenoglu’s creative samples also confirm this idea. Thus, it is used in the sense of “many”, strengthens the meaning of the thought and is used as an adverb. We do not come across this linguistic unit among adverbs in grammar books. However, one can find dozens of examples proving that it is an adverb.

The use of archaic adverbs in poetic language is also interesting. In this regard, the beautiful examples of homonymy, which is a historical category, attract attention. “There may be a relationship of homonymy between different linguistic units of the same form of the language. A number of issues of semasiology, especially the problem of the word, its meaning, are closely related to homonyms” (Dictionary of Homonyms of the Azerbaijani Language (2007), p. 5).

The author created a good mood by using the word “o başdan” in three different situations, and most importantly, by writing one next to the other and using one of the ancient and native words “obaşdan” as an adverb. This word is one of the units of the Azerbaijani language that is in danger of being forgotten. The word “dan” here is also one of the interesting national words. This word, which has passed into the archaic fund of the Azerbaijani language, has remained in the expressions “dan yeri”, “dan ulduzu”. However, recently, in the works of Bahman Vatenoglu and Zalimkhan Yagub, we have come across cases of its use as an independent lexical unit.

The work of wordsmiths in the return of our forgotten national words to our language deserves high appreciation.

The morphological features of the nouns in the poetic language are also noteworthy:

Oh drummer, play, sing,

Win my heart, sing! (Müşfig (2004), p. 123).

The word “tarchi” attracts attention as a lexeme that touches the heart and ears. Although the frequency of use of the word “tarzan” in Azerbaijani is high, “tarchi” is more national. From this point of view, words such as “madanchi” and “dastanchi” show Mushfig’s high attitude to nationality in the language. He also tried to expand the possibilities of his native language by using national suffixes in borrowed words. For example, the poet used the word “ziyanchi” instead of “ziyankar”. In general, M. Mushfig’s language is much cleaner than that of his contemporaries.

Research shows that pronouns play a major role in parts of speech. Pronouns are important morphological units in creating structural-grammatical relationships within a sentence or between sentences, clarifying and concretizing meanings, and preventing repetition in speech. In particular, demonstrative pronouns are evaluated as a text-editing factor in modern linguistic literature. Pronouns are distinguished by their compactness

compared to other parts of speech, and this feature leads to their functionality. Since a pronoun replaces all the main parts of speech, even itself, it acquires the same stylistic possibilities as the part of speech in which it is used. Demonstrative and interrogative pronouns are higher in terms of expressiveness. Demonstrative pronouns have a deictic (indicating, reporting) function, so they have various stylistic nuances. The disclosure of their main function, the determination of meaning and shades of meaning depend on the speech process, the topic and purpose of the speech.

The verb form of desire differs from other forms in terms of expressiveness and emotionality. This form shows the synthesis of many meanings. The name of this form, which is synthetic in terms of meaning, is conditional. The condition, if necessary, also expresses the meanings of the command. The fact that the form of desire expresses many meanings has resulted in giving it various names in linguistics. This form is a verb form with many names: “agreement form”, “indecision form”, “desire form”, “refusal form”, “opportunity form”, “warning form”, “command-desire form”, “imperative form”, “desire form”, etc. This is due to the richness of the stylistic shades of the verb’s desire form. One of the names of the desire form is “operative”. Operative comes from the Latin word “oprativis” and means “desired”, “desired”, “desired”. Various words are used in Russian related to this word. One of such lexical units is “optant”. This word is also of Latin origin and comes from the word “optantis”, which means “choice”, “transition”. Currently, this word is used as a legal term and gives the concept of “a person who has the right to accept the citizenship of another state”. The name “operative” of the form of desire is due to the many shades of meaning it contains and their transition to each other at different moments.

The relation of the wish form to the category of time is also interesting. The future tense is the one that best suits its essence. Although wish is a multi-semantic form, it is related to the future tense in all cases. When the wish form is used with “idi”, which forms the story of the verb forms, it does not lose the meaning of belonging to the future tense. However, the grammatical device “idi” itself has the meaning of the past tense. The use of this device with the wish form cannot connect it to the past tense, on the contrary, it intensifies the desire related to the future tense in the content of this form, or rather, semantics is felt more prominently than time:

If only I had that garden again, I would see you more often,

I would promise my pen (Mushfig (2004), p. 176).

All forms of the verb are named according to the main meaning they express. Verb forms have additional meanings in addition to the main meaning. The main meaning expresses the essence of the grammatical form. Additional meanings are formed in connection with the poetic situation.

Conclusion

In the Azerbaijani language, it is possible to find parts of speech that can carry not one or two, but more meanings. The aesthetics of the language requires poets to find and use the most appropriate of those meanings. In this regard, examples of artistic style show that poets

can achieve high-quality results from a stylistic point of view when they approach the artistic language and facts related to different layers of the language with great responsibility and caution. Giving different meanings to words, placing them in different moments and situations, and benefiting from the colorful images of language units are undoubtedly the main features of the poetic language. Sometimes we come across words with some characteristic morphological feature in the poetic language. The study shows that in poetic morphology, along with the main parts of speech, auxiliary parts of speech also have a certain stylistic role. In general, there are interesting facts in the poetic morphology of the Azerbaijani language that are worthy of investigation.

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